

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING NATIVE LANGUAGE TO HEARING IMPAIRED CHILDREN IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract: this thesis analyzes the teaching methodology of deaf pedagogy, including the methods used in the literacy process of hearing-impaired children.

Key words: deaf pedagogy, disabled children, oral speech, dactyl speech.

Introduction.

By developing oral speech as a communication tool of hearing-impaired persons, they are spiritually mature, harmonious and well-developed in all aspects, independent thinkers, have intellectual potential, deep knowledge and a modern outlook, responsible for the fate and future of our country. In order to consistently continue the task of bringing up a young generation capable of taking responsibility, to implement comprehensive measures aimed at a specific goal, and to mobilize all the forces and capabilities of the state and society in this way is expressed. L. S. Vygotsky, the theoretical founder of the modern special education system, notes that the deafness caused by hearing impairment causes the absence of human speech, and in turn, the inability to acquire speech has a great negative impact on general cultural development. R.M., who thoroughly studied children with hearing problems. Boskis shows that a relatively small impairment of the function of the auditory analyzer - whispering, limitation of the possibility of perception also hinders the normal development of the child's speech and, as a result, the formation of logical thinking.

The special method of teaching the mother tongue allows students to study the laws of the formation of language knowledge in students with hearing impairment, corrective (development of thinking and speech, teaching correct pronunciation, development of auditory perception) and educational allows solving tasks. The tasks of this textbook, based on the special methodology of mother tongue teaching in a school for hearing-impaired children, are as follows:

- clarification of the requirements for education of children with hearing impairment in the mother tongue at the modern stage;
- description of the methodological bases of the special methodology of mother tongue teaching;

- to show the connection of the special methodology of mother tongue teaching with other subjects;
- to determine the uniqueness of the modern system of teaching the hearing-impaired pupils to their mother tongue;
- to introduce the content of the tasks of the periods of teaching the mother tongue, the peculiarities of work on speech in each period;
- formation of skills for planning lessons and extracurricular activities on the formation of oral speech;
- formation of the ability to develop the development of lessons specific to different stages of education using special school programs.

In the process of special education, hearing impaired children develop the skills of accepting the speech of others, develop the skills of using speaking voice and breath, and switch to conversational speech based on the pronunciation of certain sounds, words and their combinations. The initial requirements of the course are fulfilled. Even simple listening and pronunciation of spoken speech requires a certain amount of time and responsible attention from the deaf pedagogue and children with hearing impairment. Therefore, oral speech, as an important tool for the adaptation of deaf and hard of hearing children in the hearing society, cannot fulfill the function of a communication tool in the initial period of education (preparatory group). It is not important as a primary means of live communication for deaf and hard-of-hearing children. The difficulty in teaching deaf and hard of hearing children to communicate orally and in writing with others creates the need for an auxiliary tool, for example, dactyl speech.

Through dactyl speech, the child expresses his desire, desire, and request, and at the same time, he understands the thoughts of people around him who can use dactyl speech. A child who comes to the preparatory group learns dactyl characters very quickly and even outside of class. Therefore, in the initial period of teaching, dactyl speech serves as a type of conversational speech. This allows deaf and hard-of-hearing children to develop spoken language as a means of communication and to establish speech interactions with others.

At present, the analytical-synthetic method of sounds is used in teaching literacy in public schools. It includes all the good things collected in the practice of teachers and developed according to the leading methodology. According to this method, the teacher should teach children to separate words in speech, syllables in words, and sounds in them. After distinguishing the pronunciation of the sound, the reader shows the symbol of this sound, that is, the letter. Then the children learn to make syllables and words with the new letter.

The problem of teaching literacy in the speech teaching system existing in deaf pedagogy is solved in different ways. In the mimic system, the development of the mimic speech of the deaf is implemented as a basis. Transferring mimic signs to graphic signs was used to teach them written speech. The process of teaching writing is expressed in the following ways: the subject and the concept of it are transferred from the mimic sign to the writing, in reading - from the graphic image to the mimic sign to the concept of the subject. Language teaching is based on written speech, which is seen as the basis of oral speech in the written system. In writing, one moved from a concept to its graphic symbol, and in reading, one moved from a graphic image to a concept. In the application of these two systems, teaching literacy reflects graphic images and their connection with concepts. Literacy was taught simultaneously with the development of written speech, so when talking about teaching to speak, it is also meant to teach literacy.

Oral speech lessons also make a great contribution to learning the letter system. After exchanging sounds with the children, the teacher separates the sound that requires processing and shows the image of the letter corresponding to this sound on the chart. Following the requirements of the oral speech program, deaf students know 11 letters in the first quarter, and their number increases to more than 20 in the second quarter. In the third quarter, children know all letters, compare them with their dactyl and oral pronunciation (*pronounce 17 sounds accurately, and pronounce the rest according to close reception and substitution*).

Thus, students master the processes of word analysis and synthesis from the first quarter. Learning to write is introduced later than at the same time as learning to read. This approach to teaching reading and writing is significantly different from the methodology adopted in public schools.

The analysis of the speech material should not be started at the same time as the preparatory work on the synthesis, and the formation of reading and writing skills. The approach to teaching writing will be changed. Literacy training in the deaf school is mainly based on speech material used for the development of oral speech. In these literacy lessons, work on the meaning of words is not carried out, but this situation does not exclude the work of understanding what is being read and written by students. After that, the work on illuminating its parts and the content of what was read will begin. Various activities are held to determine the understanding of what has been read:

choosing pictures, showing the content, applying practical activities of the subject, answering questions.

Matching pictures. Pupils read a phrase or part of a text and, according to the task of the teacher, show a picture corresponding to the content of what was read. The picture is specially prepared by the teacher or pictures from the book are used.

Show content. This method of content coverage is also widely used in preparatory classes. It is appropriate to apply this method of content analysis to the material in "Alifbe". For example, after reading the phrases on page 43 with the teacher, the schoolgirl, who was put on the blackboard, imitates the movements of "sit-stand".

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